

REASONS AND EXPECTATIONS OF 15-24 YEARS OLD INDIVIDUALS WITH VISUAL DISABILITY STARTING SPORTS

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Abstract:

This study was conducted on a total of 139 visually impaired athletes with different visual acuity, 15-18 aged, to define their reasons for starting sports and expectations from sports. The principle of voluntariness was taken into consideration. According to the participants' gender, disability status, branches of sports, marital status, age groups, education levels, level of income, and visual acuity, the analysis on the reasons and expectations of individuals with visual disability starting sports between the ages of 15-18 were analyzed. "The Scale of Reasons for Starting Sports and Expectations from Sports" was used as a data collection tool in the study. In this study in which analysis on reasons of starting sports and expectations from sports were done; SPSS 22.00 program, used in quantitative study, was used in this study, the data are summarized by giving percentage and frequency tables. In this study, Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was found to be 0.857. In conclusion, in this study, the reasons for starting sports and expectations from sports of 15-18 aged individuals with a visual disability were analyzed. In this sense, this study is important in terms of examining the effects of sports on disabled people and attracting attention to other individuals with disabilities. In addition, it is recommended that a new study should be carried out to evaluate the reasons for determining the reasons for starting sports and expectations from sports of other individuals with disabilities.

Keywords: 15-18 aged individuals with visual disability, athlete, reasons for starting sports, expectations from sports

1. Introduction

As long as people live together with different characteristics, there will be roles that people have to undertake, depending on many factors in society. It is called a disability to an individual's inability to fulfill these roles due to his or her status. People who are

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negatively different from their peers and who draw the attention of the environment due to these deficiencies are called people with disabilities. People with disabilities form 10% of the world population (Özer, 2001). This corresponds to an average of 500 million people (Barnes, 1998). In today's world, this rate is approximately 15% (WHO, 2016). In his studies, Hargreaves (2000) reported this ratio as around 14% in Turkey. There are more than 161 million people with visual disability in the world. Among these individuals, 124 million have low visual acuity and 34 million are blind (WHO, 2013). According to the Turkey Disability Survey (Turkey Disability Survey, 2002), "individuals with visual handicap" constitute 0,60's% of the population. Although there are many definitions and classifications related to individuals with a visual disability, the rate of loss in vision is used as a base. According to the accepted definition in both international and national literature; after all possible corrections, if the person's visual acuity is lower than 20/200, or even less than 20 (, despite the field of vision corrective lenses, they are called individuals with visual disability (Özida, 1999; Turnbull et al., 2004; Özyürek, 1995).

Sports provides an extremely important function for the integration which is aimed at reaching the special education by enabling the disabled people to come together with the disabled and the healthy people. Sports is a necessary endeavor for a healthy and happy life and is important for all people; however, sports has a different importance for individuals with disabilities. Because sports can open a new window for people with disabilities who face many obstacles in their lives and live with the stress created by these obstacles. Regardless of the type and degree of disability; movement, exercise, participation in sportive activities gives pleasure to individuals, the pleasure to act also increases the motivation of the individual's life. In addition to the positive contributions to health, the individual can share his loneliness with other people, make friends, learn solidarity, gain the ability to develop by recognizing his talents and develop positive feelings towards himself, his body and other people. All this gives the individual a chance to capture and sustain a meaningful and fulfilling life. Even individuals with disabilities can complete the training process of specially organized competition sports; participate in competitions, and experience success and failure. In this sense, they perceive themselves as athletes rather than people with disabilities. They can learn to cope with obstacles with the confidence of this emotion (Dalbudak, 2012; Özer, 2001). It can be said that sportive activities improve the psychomotor (balance, strength, speed, flexibility, physical fitness) skills of the disabled students in a positive way and make them be constructive, creative and producer. In addition, sportive activities enable the mental development of students with disabilities, teach the phenomenon of winning and losing, and the disabled person prepares himself to win and lose (Aracı, 2001). Through sportive actions, it is possible to provide morality education, sense of love, sense of sharing, environment, and methods for primitive aggression needs and actions and practices can be made (Özoğlu, 1997). Sport provides young people with strength to encounter mutual trials along with growth in a short time and to cope with problems that can confront them in their transfer to the

group of competing adults (Yiğit et al., 2017). IBSA has identified three classes in an international competition for individuals with partially visual disability or blind athletes (IBSA, 2006). Each class applies sports that can be done by the individuals with visual disability. These are;

B1. They do not see completely, they can perceive the light but they cannot recognize the shape of the hand from any distance.

B2. Although they can perceive hand, visual acuity is less than 20/600 and visual acuity is below 50 in visual environment.

B3. Visual angles are 5-200. They have visual acuity power of 20/600, 60/600 (IBSA, 2006).

Sports is the easiest way for people with disabilities to communicate with the society physically, psychologically and socially (Akdenk et al., 1997). Participating in sportive activities, acting, exercising regardless of the disability status increases the desire of people with disabilities to live. Through sports, people with disabilities can solve their loneliness, share their problems with others, learn to share friendship, learn to make common decisions, get discipline, socialize, learn to dominate, discover and develop their abilities, have positive feelings towards themselves, love life, accept success and failure to ensure that the individual continues to live (Dalbudak, 2012). Considering the concepts of human rights and equality of opportunity in the context of democracy, it is the most natural rights of individuals with disability to benefit from sports training like other normal individuals and equal opportunities should be created in this field (Atay, 1995).

The aim of this study is to determine the reasons athletes with visual disability between the ages of 15-18 for starting sports and the expectations from the sports. With this study, it was determined the reasons for visually impaired people and their expectations for sports. It is very important for the development and spread of sport and the fact that people with visual disability have independent movement and that their independence in daily life activities is due to sport.

2. Material Method

2.1. Study Group

The study group consisted of 81 male and 58 female, a total of 139 individuals with different visual acuity who are between 15-18 ages. The principle of voluntariness was taken into consideration in participation.

2.2. Collection of the Data

In the collection of the data; "The Scale of Reasons for Starting Sports and Expectations from Sports", a 2 part- "Personal Information Form" which is prepared by the researcher about demographic features were used. In the first part, students' personal information form (age, gender, educational status, sporting status, disability status, visual acuity level, level of income) is included.

In the second part; to determine the reasons for individuals with visual disability to start doing sports and their expectations from sport, “The Reasons of Athletes Tending to Branch of Athletics and Expectations (Şimşek, 2005).”, “Turkish Athletes’ Expectations from Sports and the Reasons Prompting them to Sports (Sunay & Saracaloğlu, 2003).”, and “The Factors that Effect Elite Female and Male Volleyball Players to Start Doing Sports in Turkey (Bayraktar & Sunay, 2004) were used. The Scale of Reasons for Starting Sports and Expectations from Sports (SRSSE) is a 5-item Likert scale. In the scale, for each item; the participants are asked to mark one of the options of 1-“None”, “2-“Low”, 3-“Moderate”, 4-“High”, 5-“Too high”. The score given for each item is taken as a basis.

2.3. Analysis of the Data

Each of the items in the scale is independent. Therefore, the average or total score of the scores given to the scale items was not taken. Instead, the average and standard deviations of each item in itself were used. Besides this, T-test, ANOVA tests, and frequency tests were used. The obtained data was analyzed in SPSS 20.0 packaged program. The Cronbach’s Alpha reliability coefficient of the scale was found as 0,857.

3. Findings

When the participants were examined in terms of demographic characteristics, the following findings were reached.

Table 1: Demographic Features

		n	%
Gender	Female	58	41,7
	Male	81	58,3
Level of Income	1000-2000	78	56,1
	2000-...	60	43,2
	4,00	1	,7
Education Status	Primary School	95	68,3
	High School	44	31,7
Age	15,00	32	23,0
	16,00	26	18,7
	17,00	37	26,6
	18,00	44	31,7
Branch of Sports	Bireysel Spor	38	27,3
	Takım	101	72,7
Disability Status	Congenital	68	48,9
	Afterward	71	51,1
Visual Acuity	B1	63	45,3
	B2	54	38,8
	B3	22	15,8

Table 2: Average Scores of Scale Items

	N	Minimum	Maximum	X	S
q1	139	1	5	3,13	1,13
q2	139	2	5	4,01	0,97
q3	139	2	5	4,12	0,93
q4	139	1	5	3,59	1,30
q5	139	1	5	3,40	1,25
q6	139	1	5	3,76	1,06
q7	139	1	5	3,60	1,09
q8	139	1	5	2,86	1,35
q9	139	1	5	2,86	1,45
q10	138	1	5	3,77	1,31
q11	138	3	5	4,67	0,53
q12	139	3	5	4,67	0,56
q13	139	3	5	4,70	0,48
q14	139	1	5	4,23	0,96
q15	139	2	5	4,37	0,77
q16	139	2	5	4,50	0,68
q17	139	1	5	4,37	0,85
q18	137	1	5	3,95	1,07
q19	139	1	5	3,83	1,12
q20	139	1	5	4,59	0,62
q21	139	1	5	4,27	0,94
q22	139	1	5	4,25	0,93
q23	137	1	5	4,18	0,99
q24	139	1	5	3,91	1,34
q25	139	1	5	4,21	1,07
q26	139	1	5	3,87	1,16
q27	139	1	5	4,06	1,03
q28	139	1	5	3,72	1,37
q29	139	1	5	4,00	1,03
q30	139	1	5	3,63	1,51
q31	139	1	5	3,36	1,36
Average	139	2,65	5	3,95	0,46

The T test was used for independent samples and to measure the significant difference of the answers given in the scale according to gender, the results of this analysis are given in Table 3.

Table 3: T-test According to Gender

	Female			Male			t	p
	N	X	S	N	X	S		
q1	58	3,22	1,31	81	3,06	0,99	0,83	0,41
q2	58	4,07	0,97	81	3,96	0,98	0,63	0,53
q3	58	4,14	0,94	81	4,10	0,93	0,24	0,81
q4	58	3,36	1,45	81	3,75	1,17	-1,76	0,08
q5	58	3,28	1,36	81	3,48	1,17	-0,95	0,34
q6	58	3,53	1,23	81	3,91	0,90	-2,10	0,04
q7	58	3,45	1,22	81	3,70	0,98	-1,37	0,17
q8	58	2,74	1,36	81	2,94	1,35	-0,84	0,40
q9	58	2,66	1,47	81	3,01	1,43	-1,44	0,15
q10	58	3,91	1,22	80	3,66	1,37	1,12	0,27
q11	58	4,74	0,48	80	4,61	0,56	1,41	0,16
q12	58	4,78	0,50	81	4,59	0,59	1,93	0,06
q13	58	4,79	0,41	81	4,63	0,51	2,02	0,05
q14	58	4,31	0,88	81	4,17	1,01	0,83	0,41
q15	58	4,38	0,83	81	4,36	0,73	0,16	0,87
q16	58	4,60	0,65	81	4,43	0,71	1,46	0,15
q17	58	4,43	0,86	81	4,33	0,84	0,67	0,50
q18	58	3,98	1,25	79	3,92	0,93	0,32	0,75
q19	58	3,91	1,10	81	3,77	1,13	0,77	0,44
q20	58	4,71	0,68	81	4,51	0,57	1,89	0,06
q21	58	4,34	0,98	81	4,22	0,91	0,76	0,45
q22	58	4,33	1,03	81	4,20	0,86	0,81	0,42
q23	56	4,16	1,09	81	4,19	0,92	-0,14	0,89
q24	58	3,98	1,15	81	3,86	1,46	0,51	0,61
q25	58	4,16	1,15	81	4,25	1,01	-0,50	0,62
q26	58	3,79	1,25	81	3,93	1,09	-0,66	0,51
q27	58	4,07	1,07	81	4,06	1,00	0,04	0,97
q28	58	3,78	1,35	81	3,68	1,39	0,41	0,68
q29	58	3,93	1,11	81	4,05	0,97	-0,67	0,51
q30	58	3,50	1,51	81	3,73	1,52	-0,88	0,38
q31	58	3,16	1,34	81	3,51	1,37	-1,51	0,14

As a result of the T test according to gender, a significant difference was found in q6 ($t = -2,100$, $p < 0,05$) and q13 ($t = 2,017$, $p < 0,05$) items. In S6, the score is higher in men; and in q13, the score is higher in women.

ANOVA Test was used to measure the meaningful difference of the responses given in the scale according to income levels and independent sample; the results of this analysis are given in Table 4.

Table 4: ANOVA Test According to Level of Income

	1000-2000			2000-..			F	p
	N	X	S	N	X	S		
s1	78	3,14	1,17	61	3,11	1,10	0,02	0,89
s2	78	4,05	0,97	61	3,95	0,99	0,36	0,55
s3	78	4,21	0,93	61	4,00	0,93	1,66	0,20
s4	78	3,73	1,22	61	3,41	1,38	2,10	0,15
s5	78	3,50	1,31	61	3,26	1,18	1,23	0,27
s6	78	3,88	1,08	61	3,59	1,02	2,66	0,11
s7	78	3,82	1,00	61	3,31	1,13	7,86	0,01
s8	78	2,94	1,40	61	2,75	1,30	0,62	0,43
s9	78	2,85	1,46	61	2,89	1,45	0,03	0,88
s10	78	3,85	1,43	61	3,67	1,13	0,64	0,43
s11	77	4,70	0,51	61	4,62	0,55	0,74	0,39
s12	78	4,69	0,57	61	4,64	0,55	0,31	0,58
s13	78	4,82	0,39	61	4,54	0,53	12,80	0,00
s14	78	4,18	1,11	61	4,30	0,72	0,50	0,48
s15	78	4,29	0,85	61	4,46	0,65	1,55	0,22
s16	78	4,50	0,68	61	4,51	0,70	0,01	0,94
s17	78	4,26	0,96	61	4,52	0,65	3,51	0,06
s18	78	3,79	1,17	61	4,15	0,90	3,83	0,05
s19	78	3,69	1,15	61	4,00	1,05	2,63	0,11
s20	78	4,59	0,67	61	4,59	0,56	0,00	1,00
s21	78	4,22	0,98	61	4,34	0,89	0,62	0,43
s22	78	4,13	1,11	61	4,41	0,62	3,17	0,08
s23	78	4,01	1,17	61	4,38	0,66	4,68	0,03
s24	78	3,77	1,37	61	4,10	1,29	2,09	0,15
s25	78	4,06	1,14	61	4,39	0,94	3,32	0,07
s26	78	3,74	1,18	61	4,03	1,12	2,15	0,15
s27	78	3,92	1,03	61	4,25	1,01	3,42	0,07
s28	78	3,50	1,44	61	4,00	1,22	4,70	0,03
s29	78	3,86	1,12	61	4,18	0,87	3,40	0,07
s30	78	3,47	1,56	61	3,84	1,44	1,97	0,16
s31	78	3,33	1,35	61	3,39	1,38	0,07	0,80

When the ANOVA test results were analyzed according to level of income, it was found that there was a significant difference according to level of income in q7 ($F= 7,862$, $p<0,05$), q13($F= 12,797$, $p<0,05$), and q28 ($F= 4,699$, $p<0,05$). It was stated that the individuals who have 1000-2000 level of income have been found higher in q7 and q13, the ones with 2000- level of income have been found higher in q28.

T-test was used to measure the significant difference of the answers given in the scale according to Education Status and independent samples, and the results of this analysis were given in Table 5.

Table 5: T-Test According to Education Status

	Primary School			High School			T	p
	N	X	S	N	X	S		
q1	95	3,27	1,10	44	2,82	1,17	2,23	0,03
q2	95	4,04	0,99	44	3,93	0,95	0,62	0,54
q3	95	4,15	0,92	44	4,05	0,96	0,60	0,55
q4	95	3,54	1,34	44	3,70	1,21	-0,71	0,48
q5	95	3,42	1,28	44	3,34	1,20	0,35	0,73
q6	95	3,72	1,07	44	3,84	1,06	-0,65	0,52
q7	95	3,48	1,12	44	3,84	0,99	-1,81	0,07
q8	95	2,78	1,34	44	3,02	1,39	-0,99	0,33
q9	95	2,79	1,44	44	3,02	1,47	-0,88	0,38
q10	95	3,82	1,21	44	3,65	1,51	0,71	0,48
q11	95	4,67	0,53	44	4,65	0,53	0,23	0,82
q12	95	4,66	0,56	44	4,68	0,56	-0,18	0,86
q13	95	4,68	0,49	44	4,73	0,45	-0,49	0,62
q14	95	4,07	1,00	44	4,57	0,76	-2,91	0,00
q15	95	4,26	0,83	44	4,59	0,58	-2,37	0,02
q16	95	4,47	0,73	44	4,57	0,59	-0,76	0,45
q17	95	4,35	0,82	44	4,43	0,90	-0,55	0,59
q18	95	3,87	1,08	44	4,12	1,05	-1,24	0,22
q19	95	3,69	1,11	44	4,11	1,08	-2,08	0,04
q20	95	4,54	0,67	44	4,70	0,51	-1,48	0,14
q21	95	4,35	0,86	44	4,11	1,08	1,37	0,17
q22	95	4,25	0,91	44	4,25	0,99	0,02	0,99
q23	95	4,35	0,82	44	3,80	1,21	3,18	0,00
q24	95	3,84	1,39	44	4,07	1,21	-0,93	0,36
q25	95	4,19	1,06	44	4,25	1,08	-0,31	0,76
q26	95	3,78	1,24	44	4,07	0,95	-1,37	0,17
q27	95	4,00	1,02	44	4,20	1,05	-1,09	0,28
q28	95	3,62	1,42	44	3,93	1,25	-1,25	0,21
q29	95	4,00	0,99	44	4,00	1,12	0,00	1,00
q30	95	3,48	1,57	44	3,95	1,35	-1,72	0,09
q31	95	3,24	1,40	44	3,61	1,24	-1,50	0,14

When the T-test results were analyzed according to Education Status, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 ($t=-2,233$, $p<0,05$), q14($t=-2,906$, $p<0,05$), q15($t=-2,366$, $p<0,05$), q19($t=-2,083$, $p<0,05$), and q23($t=3,184$, $p<0,05$). While the primary school students' scores are higher in Q1 and Q23; in the other questions, high school students' scores have been found higher.

ANOVA Test was used to measure the meaningful difference of the responses given in the scale according to age and independent samples; the results of this analysis are given in Table 6.

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Table 6: ANOVA Test According to Age

	15			16			17			18			F	p	Difference
	N	X	S	N	X	S	N	X	S	N	X	S			
s1	32	3,72	1,22	26	2,96	1,15	37	3,11	0,81	44	2,82	1,17	4,49	0,01	15-18
s2	32	4,19	0,97	26	3,62	1,10	37	4,22	0,85	44	3,93	0,95	2,50	0,06	
s3	32	4,38	0,75	26	4,08	1,06	37	4,00	0,94	44	4,05	0,96	1,11	0,35	
s4	32	3,50	1,39	26	3,85	1,12	37	3,35	1,44	44	3,70	1,21	0,91	0,44	
s5	32	3,56	1,32	26	3,42	1,30	37	3,30	1,27	44	3,34	1,20	0,29	0,83	
s6	32	3,88	1,04	26	3,54	1,07	37	3,70	1,10	44	3,84	1,06	0,62	0,61	
s7	32	3,63	1,24	26	3,50	0,99	37	3,35	1,11	44	3,84	0,99	1,46	0,23	
s8	32	3,00	1,27	26	3,04	1,11	37	2,41	1,48	44	3,02	1,39	1,90	0,13	
s9	32	3,00	1,34	26	2,88	1,42	37	2,54	1,54	44	3,02	1,47	0,88	0,45	
s10	32	3,56	1,16	26	3,42	1,47	37	4,32	0,85	43	3,65	1,51	3,38	0,02	16-17
s11	32	4,56	0,62	26	4,73	0,45	37	4,73	0,51	43	4,65	0,53	0,72	0,54	
s12	32	4,63	0,55	26	4,73	0,45	37	4,65	0,63	44	4,68	0,56	0,19	0,90	
s13	32	4,66	0,48	26	4,65	0,49	37	4,73	0,51	44	4,73	0,45	0,26	0,85	
s14	32	4,09	1,03	26	4,12	0,99	37	4,03	1,01	44	4,57	0,76	2,83	0,04	18-15, 18-16, 18-17
s15	32	4,31	0,74	26	4,35	0,63	37	4,16	1,01	44	4,59	0,58	2,22	0,09	
s16	32	4,56	0,67	26	4,38	0,75	37	4,46	0,77	44	4,57	0,59	0,52	0,67	
s17	32	4,53	0,57	26	4,04	1,04	37	4,41	0,80	44	4,43	0,90	1,86	0,14	
s18	32	4,19	0,82	25	3,64	0,95	37	3,76	1,30	43	4,12	1,05	2,01	0,12	
s19	32	3,84	1,14	26	3,31	1,09	37	3,84	1,07	44	4,11	1,08	2,97	0,03	16-18
s20	32	4,63	0,49	26	4,27	0,92	37	4,65	0,54	44	4,70	0,51	3,06	0,03	16-18
s21	32	4,38	1,01	26	4,08	0,80	37	4,51	0,73	44	4,11	1,08	1,77	0,16	
s22	32	4,47	0,80	26	3,88	1,07	37	4,32	0,82	44	4,25	0,99	2,04	0,11	
s23	32	4,50	0,57	25	4,12	0,93	36	4,39	0,90	44	3,80	1,21	4,15	0,01	17-18
s24	32	4,22	1,07	26	3,50	1,50	37	3,76	1,52	44	4,07	1,21	1,78	0,15	
s25	32	4,38	0,87	26	3,65	1,26	37	4,41	0,96	44	4,25	1,08	3,19	0,03	16-17
s26	32	3,81	1,38	26	3,50	1,21	37	3,95	1,13	44	4,07	0,95	1,40	0,25	
s27	32	4,19	0,90	26	3,38	1,13	37	4,27	0,87	44	4,20	1,05	5,11	0,00	16-15,16-17, 16-18
s28	32	4,06	1,16	26	3,23	1,37	37	3,51	1,57	44	3,93	1,25	2,49	0,06	
s29	32	4,09	0,89	26	3,46	1,10	37	4,30	0,85	44	4,00	1,12	3,70	0,01	16-17
s30	32	3,66	1,54	26	3,15	1,62	37	3,57	1,57	44	3,95	1,35	1,58	0,20	
s31	32	3,47	1,50	26	2,96	1,56	37	3,24	1,19	44	3,61	1,24	1,42	0,24	

When the ANOVA test results were analyzed according to age, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 (F=4,49, p<0,05), q10 (F=3,38, p<0,05), q14 (F=2,83, p<0,05), q19 (F=2,97, p<0,05), q20 (F=3,06, p<0,05), q23 (F=4,15, p<0,05), q25 (F=3,19, p<0,05), q27 (F=5,11, p<0,05) ve q29 (F= 3,70, p<0,05). In the result of the PostHoc Tests which were done to determine in which groups the differentiation occurred, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 15-18, q10 16-17, q14 18-15, 18-16, 18-17, q19 16-18, q20 16-18, q23 17-18, q25 16-17, q27 16-15,16-17, 16-18, and in q29 between 16-17 ages.

T-test was used to measure the significant difference of the answers given in the scale according to Branch of Sports and independent samples, and the results of this analysis were given in Table 7.

Table 7: T Test According to Branch of Sports

	Individual Sports			Team Sports			t	p
	N	X	S	N	X	S		
q1	38	3,58	1,18	101	2,96	1,08	2,94	0,00
q2	38	4,39	0,92	101	3,86	0,96	2,96	0,00
q3	38	4,29	0,84	101	4,05	0,96	1,36	0,18
q4	38	3,71	1,43	101	3,54	1,25	0,67	0,51
q5	38	3,66	1,32	101	3,30	1,22	1,52	0,13
q6	38	3,97	1,03	101	3,67	1,07	1,49	0,14
q7	38	3,76	1,24	101	3,53	1,03	1,10	0,27
q8	38	3,03	1,55	101	2,79	1,28	0,91	0,37
q9	38	3,08	1,62	101	2,78	1,38	1,08	0,28
q10	38	3,87	1,36	101	3,73	1,29	0,55	0,58
q11	38	4,70	0,52	101	4,65	0,54	0,48	0,63
q12	38	4,58	0,68	101	4,70	0,50	-1,17	0,24
q13	38	4,71	0,52	101	4,69	0,46	0,19	0,85
q14	38	4,26	0,92	101	4,22	0,98	0,25	0,81
q15	38	4,11	0,92	101	4,47	0,69	-2,50	0,01
q16	38	4,50	0,73	101	4,51	0,67	-0,04	0,97
q17	38	4,47	0,65	101	4,34	0,91	0,85	0,40
q18	38	4,18	1,06	101	3,86	1,07	1,60	0,11
q19	38	3,82	1,31	101	3,83	1,04	-0,08	0,94
q20	38	4,68	0,53	101	4,55	0,66	1,10	0,28
q21	38	4,47	0,73	101	4,20	1,00	1,55	0,12
q22	38	4,37	0,88	101	4,21	0,95	0,90	0,37
q23	38	4,03	1,13	101	4,23	0,94	-1,04	0,30
q24	38	3,79	1,40	101	3,96	1,32	-0,67	0,50
q25	38	4,32	0,99	101	4,17	1,10	0,73	0,47
q26	38	4,21	0,99	101	3,74	1,20	2,15	0,03
q27	38	4,16	1,15	101	4,03	0,98	0,65	0,52
q28	38	4,13	0,99	101	3,56	1,46	2,21	0,03
q29	38	4,26	0,83	101	3,90	1,08	1,87	0,06
q30	38	4,00	1,34	101	3,50	1,56	1,77	0,08
q31	38	3,92	1,10	101	3,15	1,40	3,07	0,00

When T-test results were analyzed according to branches of sports, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 ($t=2,94$, $p<0,05$), q2 ($t=2,96$ $p<0,05$), q15 ($t=-2,50$ $p<0,05$), q26 ($t=2,15$ $p<0,05$), q28 ($t=2,21$ $p<0,05$), and q31($t=3,07$ $p<0,05$). In q15, it was found that while the scores of team sports doers were higher, in the other items, individual sports doers had higher scores.

T-test was used to measure the significant difference of the answers given in the scale according to Disability Status and independent samples, and the results of this analysis were given in Table 8.

Table 8: T-test According to Disability Status

	Congenital			Afterward			t	p
	N	X	S	N	X	S		
s1	68	3,06	1,06	71	3,20	1,20	-0,72	0,47
s2	68	3,97	1,02	71	4,04	0,93	-0,43	0,67
s3	68	4,12	0,94	71	4,11	0,93	0,03	0,98
s4	68	3,68	1,20	71	3,51	1,39	0,77	0,45
s5	68	3,71	1,08	71	3,10	1,34	2,93	0,00
s6	68	3,96	0,97	71	3,56	1,12	2,21	0,03
s7	68	3,65	0,96	71	3,55	1,20	0,53	0,60
s8	68	2,88	1,31	71	2,83	1,40	0,22	0,82
s9	68	2,85	1,39	71	2,87	1,52	-0,08	0,94
s10	67	3,81	1,23	71	3,73	1,38	0,33	0,74
s11	68	4,66	0,51	70	4,67	0,56	-0,11	0,92
s12	68	4,60	0,58	71	4,73	0,53	-1,38	0,17
s13	68	4,63	0,52	71	4,76	0,43	-1,60	0,11
s14	68	4,09	0,88	71	4,37	1,02	-1,72	0,09
s15	68	4,16	0,86	71	4,56	0,63	-3,16	0,00
s16	68	4,38	0,79	71	4,62	0,54	-2,07	0,04
s17	68	4,34	0,80	71	4,41	0,89	-0,49	0,63
s18	68	3,99	1,13	69	3,91	1,03	0,39	0,70
s19	68	3,91	1,23	71	3,75	1,00	0,87	0,39
s20	68	4,56	0,56	71	4,62	0,68	-0,57	0,57
s21	68	4,31	0,95	71	4,24	0,93	0,43	0,67
s22	68	4,31	0,85	71	4,20	1,01	0,70	0,48
s23	68	4,34	0,96	69	4,01	1,01	1,93	0,06
s24	68	3,97	1,38	71	3,86	1,30	0,49	0,63
s25	68	4,37	0,99	71	4,06	1,12	1,73	0,09
s26	68	4,07	1,20	71	3,68	1,09	2,04	0,04
s27	68	4,22	1,12	71	3,92	0,92	1,76	0,08
s28	68	3,81	1,34	71	3,63	1,40	0,75	0,45
s29	68	4,26	0,82	71	3,75	1,14	3,06	0,00
s30	68	3,62	1,63	71	3,65	1,41	-0,12	0,91
s31	68	3,41	1,40	71	3,31	1,34	0,44	0,66

When T-test results were analyzed according to Disability Status, it was found that there was a significant difference in q5 ($t=2,93$, $p<0,05$), q6 ($t=2,21$, $p<0,05$), q15 ($t=-3,16$, $p<0,05$), q16 ($t=-2,07$, $p<0,05$), q26 ($t=2,04$, $p<0,05$), and q29 ($t=3,06$, $p<0,05$). While individuals with congenital disability had higher scores in Q5, q6, q26, and q29; individuals with afterward disability had higher scores in q15 and q16.

ANOVA Test was used to measure the meaningful difference of the responses given in the scale according to Visual Acuity Levels and independent samples; the results of this analysis are given in Table 9.

Table 9: ANOVA Test According to Visual Acuity Levels

	B1			B2			B3			F	p	Difference
	N	X	S	N	X	S	N	X	S			
q1	63	3,19	1,12	54	2,96	1,08	22	3,36	1,29	1,14	0,32	
q2	63	4,08	1,02	54	3,78	0,95	22	4,36	0,79	3,24	0,04	B2-B3
q3	63	4,25	0,88	54	3,91	1,00	22	4,23	0,87	2,23	0,11	
q4	63	3,65	1,32	54	3,43	1,31	22	3,82	1,22	0,83	0,44	
q5	63	3,41	1,24	54	3,28	1,23	22	3,64	1,36	0,65	0,53	
q6	63	3,73	0,94	54	3,70	1,19	22	3,95	1,09	0,47	0,63	
q7	63	3,73	0,92	54	3,48	1,22	22	3,50	1,19	0,86	0,43	
q8	63	2,86	1,29	54	2,67	1,40	22	3,32	1,36	1,83	0,16	
q9	63	2,92	1,36	54	2,65	1,49	22	3,23	1,57	1,34	0,27	
q10	63	3,76	1,13	53	3,83	1,40	22	3,64	1,59	0,17	0,84	
q11	63	4,67	0,54	54	4,57	0,57	21	4,90	0,30	3,02	0,49	B2-B3
q12	63	4,70	0,50	54	4,63	0,56	22	4,68	0,72	0,23	0,80	
q13	63	4,70	0,46	54	4,65	0,52	22	4,82	0,39	1,00	0,37	
q14	63	4,10	0,96	54	4,30	1,04	22	4,45	0,67	1,36	0,26	
q15	63	4,48	0,62	54	4,35	0,80	22	4,09	1,02	2,08	0,13	
q16	63	4,60	0,55	54	4,43	0,77	22	4,41	0,80	1,23	0,30	
q17	63	4,57	0,61	54	4,15	1,07	22	4,36	0,66	3,80	0,03	B1-B2
q18	63	4,03	1,08	52	3,83	1,02	22	4,00	1,20	0,55	0,58	
q19	63	3,98	0,99	54	3,76	1,04	22	3,55	1,53	1,43	0,24	
q20	63	4,57	0,53	54	4,56	0,77	22	4,73	0,46	0,64	0,53	
q21	63	4,25	1,08	54	4,19	0,85	22	4,55	0,67	1,18	0,31	
q22	63	4,41	0,75	54	4,00	1,10	22	4,41	0,85	3,32	0,04	
q23	63	4,30	0,94	52	4,15	0,85	22	3,86	1,36	1,62	0,20	
q24	63	4,00	1,31	54	3,83	1,30	22	3,86	1,55	0,24	0,79	
q25	63	4,43	0,93	54	4,00	1,18	22	4,09	1,06	2,56	0,08	
q26	63	3,86	1,15	54	3,87	1,18	22	3,91	1,19	0,02	0,98	
q27	63	4,29	0,83	54	3,85	1,05	22	3,95	1,36	2,80	0,06	
q28	63	3,78	1,40	54	3,41	1,45	22	4,32	0,78	3,71	0,03	B2-B3
q29	63	4,03	1,02	54	3,83	1,15	22	4,32	0,65	1,81	0,17	
q30	63	3,63	1,54	54	3,57	1,47	22	3,77	1,60	0,13	0,88	
q31	63	3,21	1,39	54	3,35	1,28	22	3,82	1,44	1,66	0,19	

When ANOVA test results were analyzed according to visual acuity levels, it was found that there was a significant difference in items of q2 (F=3,24, p<0,05), q11 (F=3,02, p<0,05), q17 (F=3,80, p<0,05), and q28 (F=3,71, p<0,05). In the result of the PostHoc Tests which were done to determine in which groups the differentiation occurred, it was found that there was a significant difference in Q2, Q11, and Q28 between B2-B3; in Q17 between B1-B2.

4. Discussion and Result

58 of the athletes with visual disability participating in the study were female and 62 were male. 78 of them have 1000-2000, 60 of them has 2000- 4000, and 1 of them has a level of income above 4000. 95 of them have primary and 44 have a high school

education. 38 of them are individual, 101 are in the team sports branch. 32 of the participants are 15, 26 are 16, 37 are 17, and 44 of them are 18 years old. 68 of them have congenital, and 71 of them have afterward visual disability. 63 of them have B1, 54 individuals have B2, and 22 of them have B3 visual acuity.

In T-test results of the scale T test according to gender, a significant difference was found in q6 ($t = -2,100$, $p < 0,05$) and q13 ($t = 2,017$, $p < 0,05$). In the 6th item of the scale item, it was found that the effect of friends and peers on the onset of sports is higher in women than that of males, and in the 13th question, women's being healthy scores are higher than males. This study does not show similarity with the results of the studies conducted by Bayraktar and Sunay (2007), and Şimşek and Gökdemir (2006). No significant difference was found between the other items of the scale. Thus, it can be understood that reasons of starting sports and expectations are different. Also, as we think that its different from the conducted studies have resulted from the fact that individuals with a visual disability have different expectations and their disabilities.

When ANOVA test results were analyzed according to the level of income, it was found that there was a significant difference in q7 ($F = 7,862$, $p < 0,05$), q13 ($F = 12,797$, $p < 0,05$), and q28 ($F = 4,699$, $p < 0,05$). In q7 and q13, individuals with 1000-2000 income level have been found higher, and in s28, individuals with 2000- income level have been found higher. The effect of an immediate vicinity coach in starting sports, item 7 in the scale, have been found higher in individuals with 1000-2000 level of income; being healthy through doing sports, item 13 in the scale, have been found higher in 1000-2000 level of income. Being a coach, in item 28 in the scale, have been found higher in 2000 and above income level. No significant difference was found in the other items of the scale. It is seen that the expectations of the individuals with disability in different level of income have changed. When the level of income of the individuals with visual disability changes, it is seen that their reasons for starting sports and their expectations have changed.

When T-test results were analyzed according to education status, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 ($t = -2,233$, $p < 0,05$), q14 ($t = -2,906$, $p < 0,05$), q15 ($t = -2,366$, $p < 0,05$), q19 ($t = -2,083$, $p < 0,05$), and q23 ($t = 3,184$, $p < 0,05$). While primary school students' scores are higher in Q1 and Q23; it was found that high school students' score has been found higher in the other items. 14th item in the scale, finding true happiness in sports; the 15th item in the scale, being aware of the positive contributions of the sports; and the 19th item in the scale, extending income level have been found higher in high school students' scores. The primary school students' score has been stated as high in the 1st item- father and siblings' effect on tending to sports and having a good physical appearance. No significant difference was found between other items of the scale. As the education status increases, we see that the expectations have changed. It is seen that the expectations of primary school and high school students are different. We can say that as the education status changes, the reasons for starting sports and expectations change as well.

When ANOVA Test results were analyzed according to age, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 ($F=4,49$, $p<0,05$), q10 ($F=3,38$, $p<0,05$), q14 ($F=2,83$, $p<0,05$), q19 ($F=2,97$, $p<0,05$), q20 ($F=3,06$, $p<0,05$), q23 ($F=4,15$, $p<0,05$), q25 ($F=3,19$, $p<0,05$), q27 ($F=5,11$, $p<0,05$), and q29 ($F=3,70$, $p<0,05$). As a result of Post-Hoc tests to determine in which of these groups the differentiation occurred; it was stated that there was a significant difference between 15-18 ages in q1, 16-17 in q10, 18-15, 16-18, 18-17 in q14, 16-18 in q19, 16-18 in q20, 17-18 in q23, 16-17 in q25, 16-15, 16-17, 16-18 in q27, and between 16-17 ages in q29.

A significant difference was found according to age groups in the 1st item of the scale- mother, father, and siblings' effect on tending to sports, 10th item-physical education and sports teachers' effect on starting sports, 14th item- finding true happiness in sports, 19th item- extending income level, 20th item- being healthy and protecting health, 23th item- having a good physical appearance, 25th item- receiving education in the level of universities related to sports, 27th item- having a earthly comfortable life, and 29th item- joining a friend group easily. No significant difference was found according to other items of the scale according to age groups. Thus, we can say that individuals with different age groups have similar reasons for starting sports and expectations. It can be said that individuals with a visual disability have different expectations in different ages, the age has an effect on emotions and thoughts; which may have resulted from the reasons for starting sports and their expectations are different.

When T-test results were analyzed according to Branches of Sports, it was found that there was a significant difference in q1 ($t=2,94$, $p<0,05$), q2 ($t=2,96$, $p<0,05$), q15 ($t=-2,50$, $p<0,05$), q26 ($t=2,15$, $p<0,05$), q28 ($t=2,21$, $p<0,05$), and q31($t=3,07$, $p<0,05$). It was stated that individuals doing team sports had a higher score in Q15, in the other items, it was seen that individual sports doers' scores were higher. The 1st item of the scale- mother, father, and siblings' effect on tending to sports, 2nd item- the effect of the desire to be a national team athlete, 26th item- maintaining relationships with the environment as a popular sports doer, 28th item- being a coach, and 31th item- the effect of school sports facility and equipment canalizing to sports have been found higher in individual sports doers. 15th item in the scale- being aware of the positive contribution of the sports has been found higher in team sports doers. Some of the results of Şimşek and Gökdemir (2006)'s study support our study. No significant difference was found in other items of the scale between individuals with a visual disability who do individual or team sports. Accordingly, we can say that the reasons for starting sports and expectations of the team and individual sports doers are similar. We can state that some items of the reasons for starting sports and expectations' of individuals doing individual and team sports being different may have resulted from their desires.

When T-test results were analyzed according to disability status, it was found that there was a significant difference in q5 ($t=2,93$, $p<0,05$), q6 ($t=2,21$, $p<0,05$), q15 ($t=-3,16$, $p<0,05$), q16 ($t=-2,07$, $p<0,05$), q26 ($t=2,04$, $p<0,05$), and q29 ($t=3,06$, $p<0,05$). While individuals with a congenital disability had higher scores in q5, q6, and q29; it was

found that individuals with afterward disability had higher scores in q15 and q16. The scores were higher in individuals with congenital visual disability in 5th item of the scale- the effect of the environment on starting sports, 6th item- the effect of friends and peers on starting sports, 26th item- maintaining relationships with the environment as a popular sports doer, and 29th item- joining a friend group easily. The scores were higher in individuals with afterward disability in the 15th item in the scale, being aware of the positive contributions of the sports, 16th item- seeing new countries. There was no significant difference between individuals' having congenital and afterward visual disability among other scale items.

The individual's having congenital or afterward disability affects the items of the scale. Thus, individuals' having congenital or afterward disability, their reasons for starting sports and their expectations are similar in certain items and are different in some of the items.

When ANOVA Test results were analyzed according to visual acuity level, it was seen that there was a significant difference in q2 ($F=3,24$, $p<0,05$), q11 ($F=3,02$, $p<0,05$), q17 ($F=3,80$, $p<0,05$), and q28 ($F=3,71$, $p<0,05$). In the result of the PostHoc Tests which were done to determine in which groups the differentiation occurred, it was found that there was a significant difference between B2-B3 in q2, q11, and q28; and between B1-B2 in q17. In these items; 2nd item- the effect of the desire to be a national team athlete on starting sports, 11th item- loving sports, 28th item- being a coach, no significant difference was found according to o B2-B3 visual acuity levels. In the 17th item- making use of spare times through doing sports, there was a significant difference according to B1- B2 visual acuity levels. Among other items of the scale, no significant difference was found according to B1-B2-B3 visual acuity levels. As visual acuity levels change, we see that the reasons for starting sports and expectations of the individuals with a disability differ in the scale items. Even though individuals with a visual disability have different visual acuity levels, we can say that they have different reasons and expectations, and other items are similar. Although the visual degrees of individuals with a visual disability are different, as there is no significant difference in reasons for starting sports and expectations, we can say that emotions and thoughts are the same.

The experiences obtained through movements are not an aim in themselves; but they are a basic tool that is continuous and effective in growth and development (Kınalı, 2003). The positive effect of sports includes individuals with disabilities in the society, as well as their physical and mental development and enables them to establish better relations within the society (Savucu et al., 2006). Physical education and sporting activities enable individuals with disabilities to control their feelings such as aggression, anger, and jealousy, which arise as a natural consequence of their disabilities and the attitude of the society towards them (Kınalı, 2003). This can be said that sports is very important for the development and spread of sports for individuals with disabilities.

In future research, it is recommended to evaluate the reasons and expectations of the athletes with visual disability to start doing the sports on the other individuals with a disability. In addition, it is recommended that a new study should be carried out to

evaluate the reasons and expectations of athletes with visual disability and other individuals with disabilities on how to start doing sport.

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